

Polarographic Behaviour and Determination of Dichromate Ions in Absence and Presence of Cadmium(II) Ion in Thiel Buffer Solutions

S. A. EL-SHATOURY*, M. H. WAHDAN and R. M. HASSAN

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, 71516 Egypt

Manuscript received 3 September 1993, revised 22 March 1994, accepted 12 May 1994

The polarographic behaviour and determination of dichromate ions have been investigated in thiel buffer solutions of pH 2.75, 4.16, 5.22 and 7.2. The reduction of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions takes place via single, or three waves depending upon the pH value. Microcoulometric experiments have been performed at the obtained limiting current region of the different waves at various pH values. The mechanism of the reduction occurring at the D.M.E. has been deduced and interpreted. A method for analytical determination of Cr^{VI} on both the micro- and macro-scales is reported. Analysis of a binary mixture $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ in thiel buffer solution at pH 2.75 is also investigated.

Numerous studies have been performed for the electro-reduction and determination of chromate ions in different media¹⁻³. The present work reports the polarographic reduction and determination of hexavalent chromium ion in simple solutions as well as in binary mixtures together with divalent cadmium ion in thiel buffer solutions.

Results and Discussion

Polarography of hexavalent chromium : The polarographic behaviour of $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ hexavalent chromium ion in thiel buffer solutions of pH varying from 2.75 to 7.2 are shown in Fig. 1. The results obtained at pH's 2.75 and 4.16 indicated that the electroreduction of $0.5 \text{ mM } \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions occurred through two polarograms (a) and (b) respectively. Each of these polarograms composed of one wave distorted by polarographic maximum was suppressed in the presence of 2.93×10^{-4} and $9.7 \times 10^{-5}\%$ resorcinol as maximum suppressor respectively. The number of electrons n , i_d and $E_{1/2}$ have been calculated from the log plot analysis of the different waves (Table 1). All the i_d values have been corrected for the dilution factor. Accordingly, Cr^{VI} species were reduced to the trivalent state. The fact that the single waves obtained at pH's 2.75 and 4.16 are not separated, may be attributed to the very limited stability of Cr^{III} species at the pH's 2.75 and 4.16, since it is well-known to be more stable

Fig. 1. Polarograms of $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ in thiel buffer solutions of pH X in presence of Y% resorcinol.

in acidic medium over a limited region from potential vs pH diagram⁴.

Increasing the pH of the supporting electrolyte to 5.22 and 7.20, indicates that each of the two polarograms obtained (c and d, Fig. 1) consisted of three waves, the first of which starts at 0.0 V (SCE) and represents the transformation of Cr^{VI} species to Cr^{IV} through the uptake of two electrons. The first and second waves can be shown as a composite waves or two intermingling waves representing successive

TABLE 1 – KINETIC PARAMETERS OF THE ELECTROREDUCTION OF $5 \times 10^{-4} M Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ IN THIEL BUFFER SOLUTIONS*

pH	2.75		4.16		5.22			7.2	
Wave	Single	Single	1st	2nd	3rd	1st	2nd	3rd	
i_d (μA)	10.4	9.7	6.6	3.2	10	5.6	3.2	7.8	
i_d/e (μA)	3.466	3.233	3.3	3.2	3.47	2.8	3.2	2.60	
n/e	~3	~3	2	1	3	2	1	3	
$E_{1/2}$ (S.C.E.)	-0.06 V	-0.08	-0.05	-0.28	-1.62	-0.15	-0.48	-1.99	
S (V^{-1})	<i>u</i> 7 <i>L</i> 16.1	<i>u</i> 6.25 <i>L</i> 15.4	16.1	10.28	10.8	<i>u</i> 5.4 <i>L</i> 14.67	<i>u</i> 14 <i>L</i> 6	<i>u</i> 6 <i>L</i> 7	
K^* ($\times 10^3$)	<i>u</i> 13.68 <i>L</i> 4.469	<i>u</i> 10.74 <i>L</i> 3.6	6.14	2.56	2.733	<i>u</i> 4.8 <i>L</i> 3.81	<i>u</i> 2.78 <i>L</i> 6.73	<i>u</i> 2.45 <i>L</i> 2.185	
αn_a	<i>u</i> 0.42 <i>L</i> 0.97	<i>u</i> 0.375 <i>L</i> 0.921	0.966	0.617	0.648	<i>u</i> 0.343 <i>L</i> 0.88	<i>u</i> 0.84 <i>L</i> 0.36	<i>u</i> 0.36 <i>L</i> 0.42	
(X)	0.50	0.48	0.5	0.375	0.286	0.64	0.428	0.4	
D ($\times 10^{-5} cm^2 s^{-1}$)	6.09	5.3	6.2141	3.977	3.086	3.39	3.88	2.488	
ΔG^* (kJ)	<i>u</i> 168.22 <i>L</i> 179.97	<i>u</i> 170.76 <i>L</i> 182.2	176.63	185.8	185.126	<i>u</i> 179.2 <i>L</i> 184.8	<i>u</i> 184.97 <i>L</i> 175.676	<i>u</i> 186.3 <i>L</i> 187.5	
$K^* D^{-1/2}$	<i>u</i> 1.75 <i>L</i> 0.572	<i>u</i> 1.48 <i>L</i> 0.49	0.78	0.406	0.492	<i>u</i> 0.825 <i>L</i> 0.4835	<i>u</i> 0.445 <i>L</i> 1.079	<i>u</i> 0.491 <i>L</i> 0.438	

* S (V^{-1}) = slope of wave analysis, D ($cm^2 s^{-1}$) = diffusion coefficient, ΔG^* = energy of activation (kJ), X = slope of Hg-height, L = lower portion of the wave, u = upper portion of the wave.

reduction stages $Cr^{6+} \xrightarrow{+2e} Cr^{4+} \xrightarrow{+e} Cr^{3+}$, whereas the third wave ($E_{1/2} = -1.62$ V and -1.99 V vs S.C.S.) represents completion of reduction stages to the chromium metal^{1,3} through uptake of another three electrons. The results obtained for the electro-reduction of Cr^{VI} in thiel buffer solutions reveal that the reduction of the depolariser passes ultimately to either the trivalent or metallic state along with one, two or three waves depending upon the pH of the supporting electrolyte as summarised in the following schemes :

Scheme I :

Scheme II :

at $pH > 4.16$, the mechanism of reduction which takes place along the three waves may be represented by the equation :

$Cr^{6+} \xrightarrow{-2e} Cr^{4+} \xrightarrow{-e} Cr^{3+} \xrightarrow{-3e} Cr\text{-metal}$
Coulometric reduction of a 1.5 mol dm^{-3} solution of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ ions in thiel buffer solutions of pHs 2.75, 4.16, 5.22 and 7.20, was established with a large mercury cathode whose potential was maintained at -0.90 V vs SCE by an automatic potentiostat. The reduction product obtained was the green form of Cr^{III} (Scheme I). The third waves ($E_{1/2} = -1.62$ and -1.99 V vs SCE) obtained at different pHs (5.22 and 7.20) may be attributed to the reduction of Cr^{III} species to the chromium metal via the uptake of three electrons (Scheme II).

Nature of reduction : The reduction of dichromate ions in thiel buffer solutions of pH values ranging from 2.75 to 7.20 was irreversible, judging from the log-plot of the wave analysis which was obtained by means of $\log i/(i_d-i)$ vs E (V) (NHE). The wave analysis was made with respect to NHE according to theoretical

consideration by Galus⁵. These plots were utilised in the evaluation of the corresponding values of the kinetic parameters⁶ and the wave characteristics including slope, αn_a (α = transfer coefficient, n_a = number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step), K° (standard rate constant), ΔG^* (energy of activation) and $K^\circ D^{-1/2}$. Table 1 summarises the kinetic parameters and micro-coulometric data for the reduction of dichromate ions in thiel buffer solutions. These results, coupled with the direct proportionality of the diffusion current to the square-root of the effective mercury column, indicate that the reduction of Cr^{VI} in thiel buffer solutions is irreversible and mainly diffusion-controlled at lower pH values (2.75 and 4.16). However, at pHs 5.22 and 7.20, the reduction of Cr^{VI} species is also irreversible and controlled by diffusion with the presence of slight kinetic or adsorption component depending on the values of the slopes (X) of $\log i_d$ vs $\log h$ (as cited in Table 1).

Effect of concentration : In order to test the validity of the polarograms for analytical purposes, the diffusion current (i_d) was measured at a constant potential value (-0.80 V vs SCE) as a function of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions at pHs 2.75, 4.16, 5.20 and 7.20 respectively. Determination of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions at pHs 2.75 and 4.16 was quite feasible under these conditions within the concentration range 0.2–1.8 mM at pH 2.75 and 0.2–1.4 mM at pH 4.16 respectively. Deviation from linearity at higher depolariser concentration was observed for the total limiting current (> 1 mM Cr^{VI}) at pH 5.22 and (> 1.2 mM Cr^{VI}) at pH 7.2. This behaviour can be explained by the adsorption of Cr^{VI} species at higher concentration of the depolariser at these pH values, which is confirmed by the values of the slope of $\log i_d - \log h$ plots and $K^\circ D^{-1/2}$ values. Constancy of i_d/c values was observed throughout the whole concentration range studied indicating the validity of Ilkovic equation.

Simultaneous determination of $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ mixture : The foregoing results reveal that the single reduction wave obtained of hexavalent chromium ion in thiel buffer solution at pH 2.75, is too wide and thus it can accommodate other depolariser waves such as Cd^{II} ions

without any interference. Cd^{II} ions produces a single wave whose $E_{1/2}$ equals to -0.65 V (SCE). In view of these interpretation, a procedure was developed for simultaneous determination of both cadmium(II) and dichromate ions in such medium in presence of 2.93×10^{-4} % resorcinol as a maximum suppressor. Analytical determination of Cd^{II} within the concentration range from 0.4 to -4.0 mM in thiel buffer solution at pH 2.75 in the presence of 0.5×10^{-3} M Cr^{VI} was quite feasible. Also polarographic determination of dichromate ions at the same pH value in presence of 0.5×10^{-3} M CdCl_2 was successful in the concentration range 0.2 to -1.4 mM $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B.D.H. make. Stock solutions (0.02 M) of both dichromate and cadmium ions were prepared by dissolving the required amount of potassium dichromate and cadmium chloride in double-distilled water, and standardised⁷. Thiel buffer solutions were prepared by mixing the appropriate amounts of the constituent reagents as recommended⁸. A 2% resorcinol solution was prepared by dissolving the required quantities in double-distilled water.

Polarographic measurements were carried out using a Universal OH-105 polarograph with three electrode system, dropping mercury electrode (DME), auxiliary platinum electrode and saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) serving as the reference electrode. The dropping mercury electrode has the following characteristics : $m = 1.236$ mg s^{-1} and $T = 4.25$ s/drop.

References

1. J. J. LINGANE and I. M. KOLTHOFF, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 852.
2. H. SADEK, R. M. ISSA and B. A. A. NABY, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1971, **16**, 401; A. V. PAMFILOV and A. I. LOPUSHANSKAYA, *Inst. Khim. Teknol.*, 1959, 103 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, **55**, 2311); M. VON STACKELBERG, P. KLINGER, W. ROCH and S. KRATH, *Tech.-Mitt. Krup forsch.*, 1939, 2 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1939, **3**, 8523); R. M. ISSA, B. A. A. NABEY and H. SADEK, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1968, **13**, 1827; I. M. KOLTHOFF and A. M. S. EL-DIN, *J Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1564.

3. D. N. HUME and I. M. KOLTHOFF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1897.
4. C. F. BASES and R. E. MESMER, "The Hydrolysis of Cations", Wiley, New York, 1976, p. 249.
5. Z. GALUS, "Fundamentals of Electrochemical Analysis", PWN-Polish Scientific Publishers, Warsaw, 1976, p. 244.
6. I. M. ISSA and M. THARWAT, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1972, **17**, 343.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Boock of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1968.
8. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4th. ed., Chapman and Hall, New York, 1952.